

Clinical Profile of Patients Admitted with Pleural Effusion on the Basis of Biochemical, Cytological and Molecular AnalysisYogita Singh¹, Sakshi Juyal², Santosh Mittal³, D.K. Vohra⁴¹Professor & HOD, Dept. of Medicine, LLRM Medical College, Meerut²Junior Resident, Dept. of Medicine, LLRM Medical College, Meerut³Professor & HOD, Dept. of Respiratory Medicine, LLRM Medical College, Meerut⁴Professor & HOD, Dept. of Medicine, SMMH Medical College, Saharanpur

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. D.K. Vohra

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Pleural effusion involves excess fluid accumulation in the pleural space and can be classified as transudative or exudative based on its cause. Accurate diagnosis is essential for effective treatment.**Objective:** This study aims to explore the clinical, biochemical, cytological, and molecular diagnostic profiles of pleural fluid to determine the causes of pleural effusion.**Methods:** Conducted at LLRM Medical College, Meerut, from April 1, 2023, to March 31, 2024, the study included patients over 5 years with pleural effusion. Data on demographics, symptoms, effusion types, causes, and diagnostic tests (ADA levels and CBNAAT) were collected.**Results:** The study involved 140 patients, predominantly male (65.7%) and younger adults. Exudative effusions were more common (64.3%) than transudative (35.7%). Tuberculosis was the leading cause (46.4%), followed by congestive cardiac failure (18.6%) and malignancy (13.6%). ADA was above reference value of >40IU in 89.2% patients of tuberculosis. CBNAAT was positive in 40% of tuberculosis cases, highlighting the need for a combination of diagnostic methods.**Conclusions:** Exudative effusions are prevalent, with tuberculosis being a major cause. ADA levels are valuable for diagnosis, while CBNAAT underscores the importance of using multiple diagnostic approaches. Comprehensive evaluation and advanced diagnostics are crucial for managing pleural effusion, especially in high-tuberculosis regions.**Abbreviations:** CBNAAT (Cartridge based nucleic acid amplification test), ADA (Adenosine deaminase), CLD (Chronic liver disease), CKD (chronic kidney disease), CCF (Congestive cardiac failure)This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Pleural effusion occurs when excess fluid accumulates in the pleural space, which normally contains a minimal amount of fluid to lubricate the lungs and chest wall.

This condition can result from either increased fluid production or decreased absorption and is classified as transudative or exudative based on the underlying cause.

Transudative effusions are typically associated with systemic conditions like heart failure, liver disease, or hypoalbuminemia, while exudative effusions result from local factors such as infection, malignancy, or inflammation.

Proper diagnosis involves differentiating between these types using clinical history, physical examination, and diagnostic tests like thoracentesis, where fluid analysis helps determine the effusion's nature and underlying cause.

Aims and Objectives

To study clinical, biochemical, cytological, and molecular diagnostic profile of pleural fluid for identifying the etiology of disease.

Material and Methods**Study Design:** This study was conducted on patients admitted in Medicine ward during one year period at LLRM Medical College, Meerut after the approval by Institutional ethics committee and informed consent from patients.**Study period:** 1st April 2023 to 31st March 2024**Sampling Frame****Inclusion Criteria**

- Patients who are willing to give informed consent.
- Patients with Pleural effusion.

- Age above 5 years.

Exclusion criteria

- Neonates and Paediatric patients < 5 years of age.

- Patients post trauma.
- Patients on Ventilatory support.
- Patients with bleeding disorders

Table 1: Socio-demographic indicators

Category	Subcategory	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	≤ 40 years	41	29.3
	41-50 years	39	27.9
	51-60 years	32	22.8
	> 60 years	28	20
	Total	140	100
Gender	Male	92	65.7
	Female	48	34.3
	Total	140	100

The table shows that the majority of patients are male (65.7%) and primarily aged 40 years or younger (29.3%). The proportion of patients

decreases with age, with 27.9% aged 41-50, 22.8% aged 51-60, and 20% over 60 years old. Females make up 34.3% of the total population.

Table 2: Chest X ray findings and its distribution

Chest X ray	No of patients	Percentage (%)
Right sided	66	47.1
Left sided	49	35
Bilateral	25	17.9
Total	140	100

The chest X-ray findings of 140 patients in our current study were 66(47.1%) had right-sided, about 49(35%) had left-sided, and bilateral pleural effusion was observed among 25(17.9%) of the patients.

Table 3: Distribution of Symptoms in patients with pleural effusion

Symptoms	No of patients	Percentage (%)
Dyspnea	82	58.5
Chest pain	49	35
Cough	43	30.7
Fever	40	28.7
Pedal edema	36	25.7
Abdominal distension	24	17.1
Weight loss	15	10.7
Hemoptysis	12	8.5
Generalized body swelling	6	4.2

The table summarizes the distribution of symptoms among patients with pleural effusion.

The most common symptom is dyspnea, reported by 58.5% of patients, followed by chest pain (35%), cough (30.7%), and fever (28.7%). Pedal

edema and abdominal distension are observed in 25.7% and 17.1% of patients, respectively.

Less common symptoms include weight loss (10.7%), hemoptysis (8.5%), and generalized body swelling (4.2%).

Table 4: Frequency distribution of type of effusion

Types of effusion	No of patients	Percentage (%)
Exudative	90	64.3
Transudative	50	35.7
Total	140	100

The table presents the frequency distribution of pleural effusion types among 140 patients. Exudative effusions are more common, accounting for 64.3% of cases, while transudative effusions make up 35.7%.

Figure 1: Distribution of causes of pleural effusion

Table 5: Distribution of causes of pleural effusion

Causes	No of patients	Percentage (%)
Tuberculosis	65	46.4
CCF	26	18.6
Malignancy	19	13.6
Empyema	8	5.7
CLD	7	5
Parapneumonic	5	3.6
CKD	4	2.9
Protein-losing enteropathy	4	2.9
Nephrotic syndrome	2	1.4
Total	140	100

The table shows the distribution of causes of pleural effusion among 140 patients. Tuberculosis is the leading cause, accounting for 46.4% of cases, followed by congestive cardiac failure (CCF) at 18.6%, and malignancy at 13.6%. Other causes

include empyema (5.7%), chronic liver disease (CLD) (5%), parapneumonic effusion (3.6%), chronic kidney disease (CKD) (2.9%), protein-losing enteropathy (2.9%), and nephrotic syndrome (1.4%).

Table 6: Value of ADA among patients with pleural effusion caused by M. tuberculosis

ADA	No of tuberculosis patients	Percentage (%)
>40	58	89.2
≤40	7	10.8
Total	65	100

ADA: Adenosine deaminase

Figure 2: Value of ADA among patients with pleural effusion caused by M. tuberculosis

Among 65 tuberculosis patients with pleural effusion caused by Mycobacterium tuberculosis, the majority (89.2%) had adenine deaminase (ADA) levels greater than 40, with only 10.8% having ADA levels of 40 or lower. This suggests

that elevated ADA levels (greater than 40) are commonly associated with pleural effusion in tuberculosis patients, reinforcing the potential use of ADA as a diagnostic marker for tuberculosis-related pleural effusion.

Table 7: Positivity of CBNAAT among patients with pleural effusion caused by M. tuberculosis patients

CBNAAT	No of tuberculosis patients	Percentage (%)
Negative	39	60
Positive	26	40
Total	65	100

The table shows the results of the CBNAAT (Cartridge-Based Nucleic Acid Amplification Test) among 65 patients with pleural effusion caused by Mycobacterium tuberculosis. CBNAAT was positive in 40% of these patients (26 out of 65), while it was negative in 60% (39 out of 65).

Diagnostic Utility: While CBNAAT provides a direct method for identifying M. tuberculosis, its lower sensitivity compared to ADA levels suggests that it should be used in conjunction with ADA testing for a more comprehensive diagnosis of tuberculous pleural effusion. ADA testing, with a higher mean value, indicates its potential in diagnosing TB-related pleural effusion, especially in cases where CBNAAT is negative.

Clinical Implication: A combined approach, utilizing both CBNAAT and ADA levels, may enhance diagnostic accuracy and help identify TB in pleural effusion cases where one method alone might fail to provide conclusive results.

Discussion

This study investigated the clinical, biochemical, cytological, and molecular diagnostic profiles of pleural fluid to identify the etiology of pleural effusion among patients at LLRM Medical College, Meerut. The findings reveal that pleural effusion predominantly affects males (65.7%) and younger

adults, with the highest incidence in those aged 40 years or younger (29.3%). The analysis of pleural effusion types showed that exudative effusions (64.3%) are more common than transudative effusions (35.7%). Notably, tuberculosis emerged as the leading cause of pleural effusion, accounting for 46.4% of cases, followed by congestive cardiac failure (CCF) at 18.6% and malignancy at 13.6%. Other causes included empyema, chronic liver disease, and nephrotic syndrome, indicating a diverse etiology. ADA was above reference value of >40IU in 89.2% patients of tuberculosis, which aid in distinguishing between tuberculous and non-tuberculous effusions. Higher the pleural fluid ADA level, the more likely the patient is to have tuberculosis, with all patients having pleural fluid ADA >70IU had tuberculosis. Additionally, the CBNAAT test results revealed that 40% of patients with pleural effusion caused by Mycobacterium tuberculosis tested positive, highlighting the importance of utilizing multiple diagnostic methods to accurately identify tuberculosis in pleural effusion cases. The negative results in 60% of the patients emphasize the need for further investigation to confirm or rule out tuberculosis. Overall, this study underscores the critical role of thorough clinical evaluation and a comprehensive diagnostic approach in managing pleural effusion, particularly in regions with a high prevalence of

tuberculosis. Future research should focus on expanding diagnostic techniques and understanding the implications of varied ADA levels in relation to different etiologies of pleural effusion.

Result

The study on pleural effusion at LLRM Medical College reveals that exudative effusions are more prevalent than transudative ones, with tuberculosis (TB) being the most common cause, affecting 46.4% of patients. The patient demographic shows a higher incidence in males (65.7%) and those aged 40 years or younger (29.3%). Symptoms like dyspnea (58.5%), chest pain (35%), and cough (30.7%) are predominant. ADA was above reference value of >40IU in 89.2% patients of tuberculosis, indicating its usefulness in diagnosing TB-related effusions. However, the Cartridge-Based Nucleic Acid Amplification Test (CBNAAT) identified TB in only 40% of the cases, suggesting that while ADA is a valuable diagnostic tool, a combined approach using both ADA and CBNAAT can enhance diagnostic accuracy for tuberculosis in pleural effusion. The findings underscore the need for comprehensive diagnostic strategies, especially in high TB prevalence regions.

References

1. Lai-Fook SJ. Pleural mechanics and fluid exchange. *Physiological reviews*. 2004 Apr; 84(2):385-410.
2. Sahn SA, Heffner JE. Pleural fluid analysis. *Textbook of pleural diseases*. 2008 Apr 25; 2:209-6.
3. Miserocchi G. Physiology and pathophysiology of pleural fluid turnover. *European Respiratory Journal*. 1997 Jan 1; 10(1):219-25.
4. Light RW. Pleural effusions. *Medical clinics*. 2011 Nov 1; 95(6):1055-70.
5. Beaudoin S, Gonzalez AV. Evaluation of the patient with pleural effusion. *Cmaj*. 2018 Mar 12; 190(10):E291-5.
6. Porcel JM, Light RW. Pleural Fluid
7. Analysis: Are Lights criteria still relevant after half a century?. *Clinics in Chest Medicine*. 2021 Dec 1; 42(4):599-609.
8. Porcel JM, Esquerda A, Bielsa S. Diagnostic performance of adenosine deaminase activity in pleural fluid: a single-center experience with over 2100 consecutive patients. *European journal of internal medicine*. 2010 Oct 1; 21(5):419-23.